

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF CARBON-BASED NANOMATERIALS ON THE THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HIGH-PERFORMANCE POLYMER FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the reinforcing effect of carbon-based nanomaterials on high-performance polymer fibres. Based on various experimental studies, which show that even with relatively high contents of carbon-based nanomaterials - despite their exceptionally high mechanical properties - only modest increases in strength are achieved, the present study investigates whether this suggests that the initially promised enhancements cannot be fully realized. The paper then extends the analysis to explore the potential for improving thermal conductivity by adding carbon-based nanomaterials. The primary focus is on reinforcing high-performance polymer fibres. Both analytical and numerical modelling are employed. The results demonstrate that, for realistic carbon nanotube (CNT) contents and aspect ratios, the extraordinary strength of CNTs cannot be fully exploited in high-performance polymer fibres. However, the addition of carbon nanoplatelets (CNPs) can significantly enhance the thermal conductivity of these fibres.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since their discovery, carbon-based nanomaterials and in particular carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [1], have been extensively studied as a reinforcement to develop composites with superior mechanical, thermal and electrical properties due to their exceptional properties [2]. However, despite their strength (~100 GPa) which is an order of magnitude greater than the strongest carbon fibre (~7 GPa), the initial expectations have not been realised [3]. Weak interfacial adhesion to the polymer matrix, agglomeration, and random orientation are some of the limiting factors [3]. A key parameter to better utilize the intrinsic properties of CNTs is to orient them along the loading axis for example by applying an electric field [4]. An alternative method is to align the CNTs during polymer processing, for example by fibre spinning [5]. In this way, polymer fibres reinforced with CNTs can be produced, with the promise of achieving superior properties [5,6]. However, while some improvement in mechanical properties is observed, none of these reinforced fibres exhibit mechanical performance comparable to that of commercial high-performance fibres.

Carbon-based nanomaterials can also be used to enhance other properties, such as the thermal conductivity of polymers or polymer fibres, due to their exceptional thermal conductivity. For example, graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) have a thermal conductivity ranging from 1000 to 5300 W·m⁻¹·K⁻¹ [7]. Significant improvements in thermal conductivity have been reported for a range of polymers. For example with 10 wt % GNPs in polyvinyl alcohol matrix, an increase in thermal conductivity of about 1800% has been reported [8].

Based on the above, it appears that carbon-based nanomaterials have a strong positive effect on enhancing the thermal properties of polymers, whereas their effect on improving mechanical properties is generally insignificant. Even in cases where a significant increase in the strength of polymer fibres is

reported, there remains the question of whether this improvement is an indirect effect resulting from a modification of the polymer matrix by the nanofiller [9].

The paper, therefore, focuses on polymer fibres and aims to address whether carbon-based nanomaterials can, even in theory, effectively reinforce such fibres in terms of strength. In parallel, it seeks to determine the maximum limits of thermal conductivity that can be achieved. CNTs will be used to address the first part of the question, and GNPs the second. Analytical and numerical models will be employed, assuming that the carbon-based nanomaterials are perfectly aligned and homogeneously dispersed within the polymer fibre.

2 MODEL DESCRIPTION

In this section, the models used in the present paper are briefly presented.

2.1 Analytical modelling of mechanical behaviour

A large number of analytical micromechanical models exist for analysing the mechanical response of aligned single-fibre composites. In the present work, the model developed by Sørensen [10], originally developed to study debonding initiation and growth from a fibre break for an infinitely long fibre, is employed (see Fig. 1). This model accounts for interface debonding, sliding due to friction, and residual stresses. Previous work has shown that modelling a single fibre (CNT) yields results similar to those obtained for multiple aligned CNTs embedded in a polymer fibre [9].

Figure 1: A single aligned CNT in a polymer fibre.

In Fig. 1, σ_c is the applied stress in the CNT reinforced polymer fibre. When σ_c reaches a critical value, σ_c^i , interface debonding initiates from the CNT end (at $x = 0$ in Fig.1). The debonding initiation stress is given by [10]:

$$\frac{\sigma_c^i}{E_c} = \frac{(1 - V_{CNT})E_f}{E_c} \Delta\epsilon^T + 2 \sqrt{\frac{(1 - V_{CNT})E_f}{E_c} \left(\frac{G_c^i}{E_{CNT} r_{CNT}} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where E_c is the Young's modulus of the CNT-reinforced polymer fibre and E_f the Young's modulus of the polymer fibre itself. r_{CNT} is the radius of the CNT and V_{CNT} the CNT volume fraction. $\Delta\epsilon^T$ is the misfit strain. G_c^i is the mode II (shear) fracture energy and influences σ_c^i . Assuming a linear softening traction separation cohesive law, the maximum interface peak traction is:

$$\hat{T} = 0.5 G_c^i \delta \quad (2)$$

where δ is the critical tangential interface separation. The frictional stress, T_{fr} , results in an increase of the applied stress, σ_c , as the debond length, λ_d , increases [10]:

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{E_c} = \frac{\sigma_c^i}{E_c} + 2 \left(\frac{T_{fr}}{E_{CNT}} \right) \left(\frac{\lambda_d}{r_{CNT}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where E_{CNT} is the Young's modulus of the CNT. The debond length is given by [10]:

$$\frac{\lambda_d}{r_{CNT}} = \frac{E_{CNT}}{2 T_{fr}} \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{E_c} - \frac{(1 - V_{CNT}) E_f}{E_c} \Delta \epsilon^T \right) - \frac{E_{CNT}}{T_{fr}} \sqrt{\frac{(1 - V_{CNT}) E_f}{E_c} \left(\frac{G_c^i}{E_{CNT} r_{CNT}} \right)} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Finite element modelling of thermal behaviour

As mentioned in the previous Section, the thermal conductivity enhancement of the polymer fibres is examined using graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) with in-plane dimensions λ_x and λ_y , and out-of-plane thickness λ_z . The GNPs are assumed to be perfectly aligned along the y -axis, forming a regular staggered 3D array within the polymer fibre, as shown in Fig. 2. The Representative Volume Element (RVE), highlighted in Fig. 2, is used to evaluate the effective conductivity of the GNP-reinforced polymer fibres.

Figure 2: Representative Volume Element (RVE) of a polymer fibre containing CNPs.

The RVE shown in Fig. 2 is analysed using the commercial finite element software Abaqus. It should be noted that, within the RVE, the outer GNPs have a thickness of $\lambda_z/2$. Periodic boundary conditions are applied using the Micromechanics Plugin for Abaqus. The effective thermal conductivity is calculated in all three principal directions.

3 RESULTS: MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF CNT-REINFORCED FIBRES

Fig. 3 shows the debonding initiation stress, σ_c^i , as function of the polymer fibre's Young's modulus, and the interface peak traction for 10% CNT volume fraction. Assuming zero interfacial frictional stresses are zero, σ_c^i corresponds to the strength, σ_f^u of the CNT-reinforced polymer fibres. These strength values can then be directly compared with the superimposed strengths of various commercial high-performance polymer fibres. The CNT Young's modulus was assumed to be 1 TPa.

If we consider the Spectra 900 fibre with σ_f^u equal to 2.1 GPa, then an interface peak traction greater than 110 MPa is required to increase the strength from 2.1 to 3 GPa (a 30% increase). However, this interface peak traction exceeds the shear strength of the fibre itself. Similar results are observed also for the Zylon HM fibre. To achieve a strength increase of approximately 30%, the interface peak traction must exceed 125 MPa. It may be added that for a CNT volume fraction of 1%, achieving a fibre strength of 3 GPa for Spectra 900 would require an interface peak traction of 200 MPa (results not shown). However, for the Zylon HM fibre, a slightly lower interface peak traction (75 MPa) is required to achieve a strength increase of about 30%. This value is still relatively high compared to the shear strength of high-performance polymer fibres.

The results above assume, as previously mentioned, the absence of frictional stresses, and therefore can be considered a lower-bound estimate of the strength of CNT-reinforced polymer fibres. Next, in Fig. 4 the effect frictional stresses is considered (Eqs. 3 and 4). It can be seen that the applied stress increases linearly with the debond length after debonding has initiated. It is assumed that the debond length increases in a stable manner; therefore, the applied stress at which the CNT is fully debonded provides an estimate of the strength of the CNT-reinforced polymer fibre.

Figure 3: Debonding initiation stress, σ_c^i , as a function of the polymer fibre Young's modulus, E_f , and the interface peak traction, \hat{T} . $V_{CNT}=10\%$, $\delta=5$ nm, $T_{fr}=0$.

Figure 4: Debond length, λ_d , as a function of the applied stress, σ_c , for different interface frictional stresses, T_{fr} . $V_{CNT}=10\%$, $\delta=5$ nm. The dashed lines show when the CNT becomes fully debonded for the corresponding aspect ratio.

In Fig. 4, the debond length is plotted against the applied stress for two different interface peak tractions (20 and 100 MPa). As expected, a higher peak traction delays the onset of debonding. Afterwards, the debond length increases linearly with applied stress. Fig. 4 also presents results for three different values of interfacial frictional stress: 0.2, 2, and 5 MPa. If we consider the case of $\hat{T}=100$ MPa and an interface frictional stress equal to 5 MPa, the strength of the CNT-reinforced fibre is approximately 5.5 GPa - an increase of about 20% compared to the stress at debonding initiation. This result corresponds to CNTs with an aspect ratio (AR) of 1000. If the aspect ratio is 5000, the strength of the CNT-reinforced fibre increases to approximately 10.1 GPa, representing an increase of about 55%. Finally, for an aspect ratio of 10000, the strength reaches 15.8 GPa - an increase of more than 70% compared to the debonding initiation stress. It should be noted that these significant increases in strength

require a high interfacial frictional stress. As shown in Fig. 4, if the frictional stress is 0.2 MPa, then the fibre strength for a CNT aspect ratio of 10000 is approximately 4.9 GPa, corresponding to an increase of only about 8% compared to the debonding initiation stress.

4 RESULTS: THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF CNP-REINFORCED FIBRES

In this section, the results for thermal conductivity of the polymer fibre reinforced with GNPs (Graphene Nanoplatelets) are presented. In Fig. 5, the principal thermal conductivity of the GNP-reinforced polymer fibres is plotted as a function of the GNPs' in-plane conductivity and the axial conductivity of the polymer fibres. Typical values for some commercial high-performance fibres (also used in the previous section on mechanical response) are 5–10 W/m·K for Dyneema fibres [11] and approximately 13 W/m·K for Zylon fibres [12]. It is worth mentioning that the thermal conductivity of isotropic (bulk, unaligned) polyethylene is around 0.3 to 0.5 W/m·K [13]. The GNP volume fraction is set to 1%. The in-plane thermal conductivity of the GNPs varies from 0 to 5000 W/m·K, with 5000 W/m·K likely representing the upper limit [14]. For practical applications, values on the order of 1700 to 2000 W/m·K are more realistic [15].

Figure 5: Principal thermal conductivity of the GNP-reinforced polymer fibre, K_c , as a function of the GNP in-plane thermal conductivity, K_{GNP} and the axial polymer fibre thermal conductivity, K_f . $V_{GNP} = 1\%$ and the aspect ratio $AR = \lambda_y/\lambda_z=500$ with $\lambda_x = \lambda_y$. The thermal conductivity is given in W/m·K.

If we consider Dyneema or Spectra polymer fibres with a thermal conductivity of 9.6 W/m·K and add 1% by volume of GNPs, the thermal conductivity of the composite fibre reaches 18 W/m·K when the conductivity of the GNP is 1750 W/m·K. If the conductivity of the GNP is 5000 W/m·K, then the conductivity of the composite fibre becomes 22.1 W/m·K. In the first case, the conductivity of the Dyneema or Spectra polymer fibres increases by approximately 1.9 times, while in the second case it increases by nearly 2.3 times. A similar trend is observed for Zylon fibres, assuming an intrinsic thermal conductivity of 13.5 W/m·K. When the in-plane thermal conductivity of the GNPs is 1750 W/m·K, the effective conductivity of the reinforced fibre increases to 22.65 W/m·K - approximately a 1.7-fold enhancement. For a GNP in-plane conductivity of 5000 W/m·K, the fibre conductivity reaches 27.61 W/m·K, representing nearly a twofold increase.

It is also interesting to consider the effect of adding GNPs to bulk isotropic polyethylene with a thermal conductivity of 0.5 W/m·K. Adding 1% by volume of GNPs with a thermal conductivity of 1750 W/m·K results in composite fibres with a conductivity of 4.6 W/m·K (more than a 9-fold increase). Adding GNPs with a thermal conductivity of 5000 W/m·K produces composite fibres with a thermal

conductivity of 6.2 W/m·K (approximately a 12-fold increase). Therefore, GNPs have a more pronounced impact when the base polymer fibre has a lower thermal conductivity..

Figure 6: Principal thermal conductivity of the GNP-reinforced polymer fibre, K_c , as a function of the GNP in-plane thermal conductivity, K_{GNP} and the axial polymer fibre thermal conductivity, K_f . $V_{GNP} = 10\%$ and the aspect ratio $AR = \lambda_y/\lambda_z=500$ with $\lambda_x = \lambda_y$. The thermal conductivity is given in W/m·K.

Fig. 6 is similar to the previous figure, but with V_{GNP} increased to 10%. It can be seen that for Dyneema or Spectra fibres with a thermal conductivity of 9.6 W/m·K, the resulting composite fibre has a thermal conductivity of 135 W/m·K (14 times higher) when the GNPs have a thermal conductivity of 1750 W/m·K. For a Zylon fibre and assuming that K_{GNP} is 1750 W/m·K, the composite fibres have a thermal conductivity of 144 W/m·K (10 times higher). The trends are similar to those described for the case where V_{GNP} equals 1%, but the thermal conductivities obtained for the reinforced fibres are now much higher. In all cases, the enhancement of thermal conductivity is greater when the starting polymer fibre has a lower thermal conductivity.

It should be noted that higher thermal conductivities can be obtained, for example, by increasing the aspect ratio whilst maintaining the same GNP volume fraction. In the present work, we have chosen to use the simplest staggered 3D distribution of GNPs and have fixed the aspect ratio, whilst also using $\lambda_x = \lambda_y$.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, the effect of reinforcing high-performance polymer fibres with carbon-based nanomaterials was investigated using simulations, with the aim of determining whether carbon-based nanomaterials can enhance the mechanical and thermal properties of the fibres.

It was shown that several conditions must be met simultaneously, such as exceptional aspect ratio of CNTs, substantial frictional stresses, and significant volume content of CNTs, in order to achieve an increase of several times (3-4 times) in the polymer fibre strength.

On the other hand, it was shown that adding only small amounts (1% by volume) of GNPs increases the thermal conductivity of polymer fibres by a factor of 2. Increasing the content of GNPs to 10% results in an increase by a factor of 15 for Dyneema fibres, using a typical thermal conductivity of 1750 W/m·K for the GNPs.

Therefore, it can be argued that carbon-based nanomaterials are promising materials for enhancing the thermal properties of polymer fibres, but not the mechanical properties.

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